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Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc. The ir spectra (KBr) of the compounds were recorded in a Backmann IR-20 spectrophotometer. The structures of the compounds were established on the basis of their elemental analysis, counter synthesis, m.m.p. and ir spectra.

The thiazoles⁶ and the benzthiazoles⁴ were prepared by the reported methods.

2-Imidazolidine thione (1): To a mixture of ethylenediamine (2.0 mol), rectified spirit (300 ml) and water (300 ml), carbon disulphide (2 mol) was added dropwise with occasional shaking for 2 h and refluxed on a water-bath for 1 h. Concentrated HCl (15 ml) was then added and further refluxed for 9–10 h. The resulting solid on cooling was filtered, washed with cold acetone (60–80 ml) and crystallised from ethanol.

2-Methylthio-4,5-dihydroimidazole (2): To 1 (1.5 ml) in requisite quantity of 2 N NaOH, dimethyl sulphate (1.5 ml) was added dropwise maintaining the temperature at 40–50° and stirred for 1 h. The contents were then cooled and extracted with ether. Ether solution was dried (anhydrous sodium sulphate) for 8 h and the excess solvent was distilled off. The resulting solid was filtered, dried and crystallised from ethanol.

2-(Benzthiazol-2'-ylamino)-4,5-dihydroimidazole (3): 2 (0.01 mol) and 2-amino benzthiazole (0.01 mol) were refluxed in rectified spirit (50 ml) for 4 h. The contents were then cooled and filtered and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol (Table 1), $\nu_{\max}$; 1 440 (C=N), 1 270 (C-N), 700 (C-S), 3 280 (=NH), 400, 650, 810, 885 and 1 100 cm^{-1} (imidazole ring system).

Biological activity: 2-(Substituted-thiazol/benzthiazolyl-amino)-4,5-dihydroimidazoles were screened for antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* and antitubercular activity against H₃₇R₇ strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*.

Studies on Synthesis of 2-(Substituted-thiazolyl/benzthiazolyl-amino)-4,5-dihydroimidazoles

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THE biological activities¹ of condensed heterocycles containing pyridine, pyrimidine, thiazole and imidazole rings, led us to synthesise some imidazole derivatives containing thiazoles and benzthiazoles as substituents. Substituted-benzthiazoles are also biologically active².

The compounds were prepared according to Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY DATA OF THE IMIDAZOLES (3)*

Ar	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %	Antibacterial activity**		Antitubercular activity***	
				<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	10 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$	100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$
Benzthiazolyl	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₄ S	135	68.80	—	—	+	—
6-Cl-Benzthiazolyl	C ₁₀ H ₉ ClN ₄ S	190	67.32	+	—	+	+
6-OCH ₃ -Benzthiazolyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₄ OS	120	66.53	+	—	+	+
6-Br-Benzthiazolyl	C ₁₀ H ₉ BrN ₄ S	195	60.60	+	+	+	+
6-(SO ₂ NH ₂)-Benzthiazolyl	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	289	65.65	+	—	+	—
4-(C ₆ H ₅)-Thiazolyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₄ S	115	67.34	—	—	+	+
4-(C ₆ H ₄ Cl)-Thiazolyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ ClN ₄ S	150	62.61	—	+	+	+
4-(C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂)-Thiazolyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₂ S	165	68.96	—	—	+	—
4-(C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃)-Thiazolyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₄ OS	158	69.09	+	—	+	+
4-(C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃)-Thiazolyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₄ S	145	68.70	+	—	—	—

*Elementary analyses found satisfactory.

(+)=Inhibition, (–)=no inhibition. *(+)=No inhibition, (–)=inhibition.

NOTES

Among all the 2-imidazoline derivatives only four compounds are inactive against *S. aureus* and the rest are active. Many compounds were found active against *S. aureus* in comparison to *E. coli*. Only two compounds were active against *E. coli* having substitution 6-bromobenzthiazolyl and 4-chlorophenylthiazolyl to imidazole ring and the others found inactive against the same gram -ve bacteria.

The same 2-imidazoline derivatives were screened for antitubercular activity against H₈₇R_v strain of *M. tuberculosis*. Only two compounds having substitution 6-sulphonamidobenzthiazolyl and 4-methylphenylthiazolyl to the imidazole ring were found active at lower concentration (10 µg ml⁻¹), five compounds active at higher concentration (100 µg ml⁻¹) and two compounds active at both the concentrations (Table 1).

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Mannich Bases of Ethyl 5-Substituted-benzimidazole-2-thioacetate and their Anti-inflammatory and Analgesic Activities

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WIDE range of biological activities¹ are reported with various benzimidazole compounds. Some benzimidazole-2-thiones, 1,3-disubstituted benzimidazole-2-thiones and thioesters are reported to exhibit analgesic and antiinflammatory activities².

The title compounds were thus prepared for evaluating their analgesic and antiinflammatory activity.

The benzimidazole-2-thiones and their 5-substituted analogues were synthesised by the reaction of *o*-phenylenediamine or 4-substituted-*o*-phenylenediamine using CS₂ in presence of ethanolic KOH³. Their corresponding 2-thioacetic acid ethyl ester was prepared using chloroacetic acid, KOH, ethanol and HCl gas.

The title compounds (2) were obtained from 1 by reacting with various amines in presence of aqueous 40% formaldehyde solution following standard procedure of Mannich reaction.

R = H, CH₃, OC₂H₅.

R' = *N*-Morpholine, *N*-Piperidine,

N,N-Dibutyl, *N,N*-Dicyclohexyl

A mixture of 1 (0.01 mol) was taken in methanol (50 ml) and to it formalin (40% aqueous, 0.02 mol) was added followed by the secondary amine (0.01 mol) with stirring for 3 h. The solvent was evaporated on a water-bath to get a crude product. It was decolourised by refluxing with activated charcoal in methanol and crystallised from methanol-acetone mixture.

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 377 spectrophotometer; $\nu_{\max}$ 1 170 (C-O stretch for ethoxy), 1 110-1 240 (C-O-C), 1 180-1 200 (C=S) and 1 385 cm⁻¹ (CCH₃). Uv spectra (EtOH) were recorded on a Ultrospec 4050 spectrophotometer (Table 1). The elemental analyses were carried out at N.S.I.C., Nagpur and the C and H data were found satisfactory. The purity and homogeneity of the compounds were checked by tlc. The results are recorded in Table 1.

Analgesic activity: The activity of compounds was determined by writhing method⁴. A group of albino mice of either sex, weighing 20-24 g were used. Suspension of the compounds and aspirin (standard drug) was prepared in 10% Tween-80 and were administered at 30 mg/kg does (150 mg/kg for aspirin) intraperitoneally. After 30 min later 300 mg/kg of 3% acetic acid was administered to each animal and writhing recorded for 20 min. The